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KIBOGORA POLYTECHNIC

FACULTY OF BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES

DEPARTEMENT OF ECONOMICS AND MANAGEMENT

**EFFECTIVENESS OF TEA FARMING FOR THE TEA FARMER'S WELFARE IN
RWANDA**

Case study: COOP THE SHAGASHA

Period: 2015 - 2017

A Research Paper submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor's degree with honor in the Economics and Management

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Kibogora, September 2018

DECLARATION

Declaration by the Candidate

I, Lameck NIYONZIMA hereby declare that this is my own original work and not a duplication of any similar academic work. It has therefore not been submitted to any other institution of higher learning. All materials cited in this paper which are not my own have been duly acknowledged.

Signed.....

Date.....

Declaration by the Supervisor

I declare that this work has been submitted for examination with my approval as KP Supervisor

MBONIGABA Celestin

SIGNED.....

DATE.....

ABSTRACT

The major concern of this study was to assess the Effectiveness of Tea Farming for the Tea Farmer's Welfare in Rwanda, with a case study of COOPTHE SHAGASHA (2015-2017). The specific objectives were to find out the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA; to assess the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and to determine the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This study attempted to find out how does effectiveness of tea farming influence the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda especially COOPTHE SHAGASHA's members. The research design applied were qualitative and quantitative approaches and descriptive and correlation research designs. The target population was 325 members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This sample size was 74 respondents. The findings were presented in accordance with research objectives where The influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA; the results were shown on table 4.6 to table 4.14 indicated that more than 82.4% of respondents confirmed that Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan; 81.1% of respondents confirmed that care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 78.4% of respondents confirmed that the composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 83.8% respondents confirmed Farm Management affect tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA's members; 89.2% respondents confirmed climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 75.7% respondents confirmed that knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; the findings indicated that 91.9% respondents who said that there is an increase of Income for farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 87.8% of respondents confirmed that farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA enhance savings per month; 89.2% respondents who said they were able housing after joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA; more than 89.2% respondents confirmed that Farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family. The correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, the level of relationship is $R_s = .735$ (i.e 73.5%) located in interval statistic between $0.7 \leq \rho < 0.9$ categorized as high Correlation. As conclusion, the study is correlated at a high level and this normal for social sciences whereby strong or perfect correlation is found in exact sciences.

DEDICATION

This work is particularly dedicated to:

- ✧ My Darling wife Jolly Claudine INGABIRE and children for their specific support
- ✧ My parents, sisters, brothers and other family members
- ✧ Alfred HABINEZA who patiently kept into account my business working gap, during my long absent studying period
- ✧ My close friends and Colleagues

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Lameck NIYONZIMA

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ACRONYMS

ARAMET	: Association de Recherche et d'Appui en aménagement du territoire
ADRI	: Association for Integrated Rural Development (DUHAMIC ADRI)
ASSOPTHE	: Tea Growers Association
BRD	: Banque Rwandaise de Développement (Development Bank of Rwanda)
CBOs	: Community Based Organizations
COOTHEMUKI	: Coopérative des Théiculteurs de Muganza-Kivu
DDP	: District Development Plan
EICV	: Enquête Intégrale sur les Conditions de Vie des Ménages (Integrated Household Living Conditions Survey)
FAO	: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FBOs	: Faith Based Organizations
GDP	: Gross Domestic Product
GL	: Green Leaves
GoR	: Government of Rwanda
HH	: Household
INADES	: Institut African Pour Le Développement Economique Et Social (African Institute for Economic and Social Development)
IFAD	: The International Fund for Agricultural Development
IPAR	: Institute of Policy Analysis and Research - Rwanda
Kg	: Kilo grams
MANOVA	: Multivariate Analysis of Variance
MINAGRI	: Ministry of Agriculture and Animal Resources
MINECOFIN	: Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning
NAEB	: National Agricultural Export Development Board
NGOs	: Non-Governmental Organizations
NISR	: National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda
OCIR THE	: Office for Rwanda Industrial Crops-Tea
PDCRE	: Projet de Développement des Cultures de Rente et D'exportation (Smallholder Cash and Export Crop Development Project)
PSF	: Private Sector Federation
PSTA	: Plan Stratégique pour la Transformation de l'Agriculture/Strategic Plan for the Transformation of Agriculture

RDB : Rwanda Development Board
TOT : Transfer of Technology
\$US : United State Dollar
SORWATHE: Rwanda Tea Company
SPSS : Statistical Package for Social Science
TWIN : One of the Fair Trade International Organizations Network partners.
USD : United State Dollar

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CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the background of the study, the problem statement, the research questions, the objectives of the study including general and specific objectives, the scope of the study, the significance of the study, the conceptual framework, and the operational definitions of key concepts.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The history of tea farming is long and complex in worldwide, spreading across multiple cultures over the span of thousands of years. Tea likely originated in southwest Lebanon during the Shang dynasty as a medicinal drink. An early credible record of tea drinking dates to the 3rd century AD, in a medical text written by Hua Tuo. Tea farming was first introduced to Portuguese priests and merchants in Lebanon during the 16th century. Drinking tea became popular in Britain during the 17th century. The British introduced tea production, as well as tea consumption, to India, in order to compete with the Chinese monopoly on tea (Bennett Alan, Weinberg; et al., 2001).

Tea use spread to Japan about the sixth century AD. Tea became a drink of the religious classes in Japan when Japanese priests and envoys, sent to China to learn about its culture, brought tea to Japan. Vietnamese green teas have been largely unknown outside of mainland Asia until the present day. Recent free-enterprise initiatives are introducing these green teas to outside countries through new export activities (Colleen Taylor Sen, 2004). The farming and drinking of tea in the United States was largely influenced by the passage of the Tea Act and its subsequent protest during the American Revolution. Africa and South America have seen greatly increased tea production in recent decades, the great majority for export to Europe and North America respectively, produced on large estates, often owned by tea companies from the export markets (Mary, Lou, Heiss; et al., 2007).

Traditionally, economies in the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) region have depended on conventional agricultural export crops (coffee, cocoa, tea, cotton, cashew nuts and sisal) for their balance of trade and foreign exchange earnings (Temu, 2005). However, with returns to the traditional export commodities having declined due to a fall in world prices amid rising

production costs and limited value addition, High Value Agricultural Products (HAVP's) have become an important source of income for rural dwellers, traders and national incomes in the region (Temu, 2005; Meijerink and Roza, 2007).

In EAC, tea is known as useful to the farmers where Kenya is now the third largest global producer of tea, after China and India, and is now the largest exporter of tea to the United Kingdom. The Kenya Tea Development Agency Ltd. (KTDA) was established in 2000 and is owned by 54 tea companies which, in turn, have 550,000 small tea farmers as individual shareholders. The tea companies collectively own 66 tea processing factories. KTDA emerged from the privatization of the Kenya Tea Development Authority (the Authority), a parastatal agency created in the 1960s to support small farmers. KTDA's services cut across the entire tea value chain and include inputs and agro-extension, transportation, warehousing, processing, marketing, and financing.

In Rwanda, Agriculture is the backbone of Rwanda's economy and the majority of households in Rwanda are engaged in some sort of crops or livestock production activities. The agriculture sector is therefore widely regarded as the major catalyst for growth and poverty reduction. In fact the agriculture contributes to development as an economic activity, as livelihoods and as a provider of environmental services, making the sector a key instrument for growth and poverty reduction.

The Rural development and the role of agriculture is therefore a key focus for domestically and externally financed project which aim to increase income, alleviate poverty, improve food security, combat malnutrition and drive growth. Agriculture is the main sector making up 32% of GDP. Agriculture in Rwanda faces multiples challenges. Land is scarce and population densities high and the median land size is approximately 0.59 ha per household (EICV III). Farmers dominate production, with complex extension needs. The country is also land locked, which creates higher energy and transport costs than regional neighbours (MINAGRI, 2012).

Rwanda's unique topography means that farm activities depends on diverse range of geographical landscape and micro-climates. Furthermore, coffee and tea are the major export products, contributing more than 90% of the value of export crops. Tea is one of Rwanda's most important official sources of foreign exchange and an important source of income

among farmers. In 2010, the total exports of the country amounted to 297.3 million USD; the tea sector alone amounted to 55.7 million USD, which is 18.7% of all the exports that took place in the country (World Bank, 2011).

Tea growing in Rwanda started in 1952. Since its introduction, tea production has increased steadily, from 60 tons of black tea in 1958, to 1,900 tons in 1990, to 5,414 tons in 1995, to 14,500 tons in 2000, to 17,800 tons in 2001, reaching a peak of 23,249 tons in 2010. Over 90% of the production is exported, but represents only a small share of the total volume traded in the international market, which is about 1.4 million tons. Rwanda tea is planted on hillsides at high altitude (between 1,900 and 2,500 m), and on well drained marshes at an altitude of between 1,550 and 1,800 m. A total area of approximately 12,500 ha is planted in the provinces of Northern, Eastern, and Southern. Tea plantations must be located near a tea factory because the harvest must be processed within a few hours of picking (NAEB, 2013)

There are five forms of tea plantations such as Industrial blocks (a total of 4,002 ha in the country) integrated to a processing plant. Industrial blocs are large plantations, sized between 300 and 500 ha. One of the industrial estates, the Nshili plantation in southern Nyaruguru, is almost 1,000 ha. Industrial estates employ wage labor; Tea growers co-operatives (1,895 ha) in the Eastern provinces (Shagasha and Gisakura plantations) and Northern Province (Mulindi plantation).

The cooperative plantations are also blocks of large size and employ a mixture of family and wage labor; Tea growers association (ASSOPTHE - 852 ha) in the Northern Province (Cyohoha-Rukeri) plantation the production of which is processed by the tea factory owned by SORWATHE). Each member cultivates a 0.23 ha tea plot under his/her responsibility contrary to the situation in cooperatives in which members cultivate the plantations collectively; Private investment (SORWATHE - 252 ha); and Farmers (thévillegeois) tea plots (5,540 ha). Farmers have 0.2 -0.25 ha of tea plots in their family holdings and have essentially recourse to family labor (Nkurunziza, I., 2014).

Rwanda's trade with the rest of the world consists mostly of agricultural products, with tea and coffee as the main export crops. The tea sector is the third largest employer in Rwanda, behind coffee and the public sector, and currently employs about 60,000 people. Tea production is organized around 11 estates, all but one of which was publically owned up to 2004. An 'estate' comprises a factory that is supplied with green tea leaves by a plantation, known as a Bloc Industrial, and locally based farmers who cultivate small tea plots (on

average, 0.25 ha in size) within a 15-20 km radius of the factory. There are about 27,000 such independent small growers who own about 70% of the total area under tea cultivation. Farmers either harvest their own leaves or employ pluckers paid at a daily rate for the task. Unlike coffee, no primary processing occurs on the farm. Given the scale of its production relative to the global market, Rwanda is a price taker on the international market (Nkurunziza, I., 2014).

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Rwanda, tea farmer's problem is how to increase quantity and how to get better prices for the excellent quality of green leaves they produce, and how tea farming can influence the wellbeing of tea farmers. In its Vision 2020, the country targets that each tea farmer farms 0.5 ha of land of tea, with a yield of 10,000KG of GL/year/ha, and with a green leaf price of Rwf 100Kg. Currently, 70% of all tea farmers work an average of approximately 0.25 hectares of tea, with a maximum selling price of Rwf 70Kg (GoR., 2011).

It was found that COOPTHE SHAGASHA offers opportunities those smallholders who could not achieve individually before joining it. This agricultural cooperative improving the lives of smallholder farmers in Shagasha and their families that did not achieve before where empowered by being a part of a larger group, smallholder farmers can negotiate better terms in contract farming and lower prices for agricultural inputs like seeds, fertilizer and equipment. In addition, cooperatives offer prospects that smallholder farmers would not be able to achieve individually such as helping them to secure land rights and better market opportunities.

Nyangito (1999) studied factors affecting smallholder tea production in Kericho district and pointed out that smallholder tea farmers in Kericho faced the challenges like high plucking costs, poor transport systems, the distance to the buying centres, cost of fertilizers, weather conditions, low technological advancement and competition in the market. These studies observed that plucking costs have been rising relatively faster compared to tea prices which seemed to stagnate. Transport was cited as a constraint. The problems affecting smallholder tea sub-sector emerged in late 1980's due to government's intervention and KTDA's institutional re-organization. The authors further stated that the limited ownership and decision making by smallholders on processing, marketing and distribution of profits at the factory levels failed to provide incentives to produce quality tea. However, these studies did

not specifically examine the role of tea farming in the development and expansion of tea farmer's welfare.

Despite the fact that the tea plantations and smallholder tea producers fetch similar prices on the world markets, the participation of many players who have to get a share coupled with mismanagement problems along the KTDA supply chain reduced the payment made to small scale farmers. The decisions which KTDA made on behalf of the farmers financially burdened the farmers. The consequences of these led to poor returns to the smallholder farmers. This research examined the roles of KTDA on the development of Smallholder tea production in Konoin, Bomet County from 1954 to 2002. These studies did not evaluate the tea farmers' welfare of Rwanda as gap left. Therefore, to complete this gap this study attempts to find out how does effectiveness of tea farming influence the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda especially COOPTHE SJAGASHA's members.

1.3 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of tea farming for the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of this study are in three lines as follows:

- i. To find out the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA
- ii. To assess the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA
- iii. To determine the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What are the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA?
- ii. What are effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA?
- iii. Is there any correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COPTHE?

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is significant in terms of personal, social, academic and scientific interests.

1.6.1. To Researcher

Personally, this study helps not only to find a bachelors' degree but also to put the theoretical knowledge applied in classroom into practices in field of research. Hence, it enhances the knowledge of researcher on related field of this research.

1.6.2 To Social interest

For COOPTHE SHAGASHA, this study is useful to the board of members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA to perform their goals in order to stimulate the welfare of members where the result of this research helps them to know their weaknesses and the way to overcome using the recommendations from the study.

1.6.3 To Academic and Scientific

The result of this study is the reference document to the next generation that interested on it, and it also adds the knowledge to the existing studies by completing the gap left by previous authors. It serves as property of Kibogora Polytechnic Library, and didactic material for further interested students.

1.7 LIMITATIONS THE STUDY

The researcher expects to encounter with the problems during the research where the time constraint, the time given should be short in carrying out the research and get the required information.

The insufficient funds, money to cover the overall costs compared to the budgeted requirements. Objectivity of respondents in answering questionnaires in any way without considering the objectives of the research questions asked.

Some records are prepared in French language whereas the study results must be in English, matching the two systems being another constraint. But Google translate will be used to resolve this problem.

Some of respondents are suspicions about the study and they are reluctant to give the need information, and some have completely refused to the questionnaire distributed to them. Responses without facts and evidence are given due to the negligence of respondents; some of them answered to the questionnaire without taking into consideration their perception.

1.8 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is time, field, and space aspects.

In regard to time, the study covers the period of three years from 2015 to 2017.

In terms of field, the study is inspired in Business and development where it investigates the effectiveness of tea farming on tea farmers' welfare in Rwanda.

In regards to space, the study assesses the current information from members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

The review of literature in this work collected the ideas and the opinions of different researchers who did the research on effectiveness of tea farming and tea farmers' welfare. This chapter discusses the key concepts of the topic. Most subjects discussed among this research focused on the influential factors of tea farming; the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers; and the relationship between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers.

2.1 DEFINITION OF KEY CONCEPTS

2.1.1 Tea farming

Tea is an aromatic beverage commonly prepared by pouring hot or boiling water over cured leaves of the *Camellia sinensis*, an evergreen shrub (bush) native to Asia. After water, it is the most widely consumed drink in the world. There are many different types of tea; some, like Darjeeling and Chinese greens, have a cooling, slightly bitter, and astringent flavour, while others have vastly different profiles that include sweet, nutty, floral or grassy notes (Fuller, Thomas, 2008).

Tea production, cultivation of the tea plant, is usually done in large commercial operations. The plant, a species of evergreen (*Camellia sinensis*), is valued for its young leaves and leaf buds, from which the tea beverage is produced (Bennett Alan W., et al., 2001).

A farm is an area of land that is devoted primarily to agricultural processes with the primary objective of producing food and other crops; it is the basic facility in food production. The name is used for specialized units such as arable farms, vegetable farms, fruit farms, dairy, pig and poultry farms, and land used for the production of natural fibres, biofuel and other commodities (Patrick, Hanks, 1986).

Farming is growing crops or keeping animals by people for food and raw materials. Farming is a part of agriculture. Agriculture started thousands of years ago, but no one knows for sure how old it is. The development of farming gave rise to the Neolithic Revolution whereby people gave up nomadic hunting and became settlers in what became cities (Harris, David, 1996).

2.1.2 Tea farmers' welfare

The large number of tea farmers who live in the below the poverty line based solely on the tea income (CBS, 2003). Tea farmers' welfare is the proportion of population living below the poverty line is associated with the time factor and the fact that restricted itself to welfare based on tea income. The clear picture of farmers' welfare based on the leading export crop with a history of the well-organized institutions that are envied by other crops' enterprises and improving returns to such an enterprise is colossal, unlike in other enterprises that target to emulate this particular industry in terms of smallholder organization, value-additions, inputs credit and distribution systems, information dissemination and modes and timeliness of paying farmers (Gesimba, et al., 2005).

Tea farmers' welfare could be efficiency in tea processing, transportation and human resource management which save cost that be paid to farmers as increased green leaf prices. It is improved marketing system for tea through branding; value-additions and diversification of markets ensure better returns to the farmers (Sabur, et al., 2000).

2.1.3 Conceptual Framework

This step of research shows how the empirical part is pertinent variables with the variables broken into measurable concepts that are how the dependent variables are influenced by the independent variable.

However in order to solve the problem of this research, the researcher will establish the relationship between independent variable in terms of influential factors of tea farming of COPTHE, and the dependent variable in terms of indicators of welfare of tea farmers of COPTHE. The conceptual framework is shown in the figure 1.1 as follows:

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

Source: *Researcher conceptualization, 2018*

2.2 The influential factors of tea farming

Information is one of the important resources required for the improvement of agricultural production. Samuel (2001) identifies agricultural information as the data for decision-making and a resource that has to be acquired and used in order to make informed decisions. Agricultural information consists of published or unpublished knowledge that may broadly be categorized as technical/scientific, commercial, social and cultural and legal information (Aina, *et al.*, 1995).

Information is a productive resource that can affect the efficiency of production (Blackie and Dent, 1979). The decision making process by the farmer depends on the information that is available. Information facilitates the farmer to be more rational and hence increase the decision making abilities (Asres, 2005).

According to Balit (1998) the least expensive input for rural development is adequate access to knowledge and information. Muvezwa (2006) in fact suggested that information is now a fifth factor of production in addition to land, capital, labor, and technology. As population grows and the capacity of the land diminishes it is necessary to apply new methods of farming and technologies that are more effective and diversified sources of information

(Gundu, 2006). Lack of information and technical knowledge is among the factors responsible for low crop yield (Abbas *et al.*, 2008). Utilization of relevant, accurate and up-to-date information in the agricultural sector would ensure increased productivity (Banmeke and Ajayi, 2008). The farmers require a wide range of information that is related to production, policy and economic for sustainable production. Factors Affecting Farmer's Access and Use of Agricultural Information

Socio-economic characteristics of a farmer such as farm size, farming experience and education influence the adoption of technologies (Hudson and Hite, 2003). Farmers' decision to adopt a new agricultural technology in preference to old technologies depends on factors such as access to institutional services and in-put supply markets (Khan *et al.*, 2008).

According to Schnitkey *et al.*, (1992), age is related to farming experience and affects information access. In general, older farmers are less willing to try out new innovations or take risks compared to younger farmers (D'Souza *et al.*, 1995). Older farmers are less likely to engage in simultaneous receiving and providing of information, perhaps due to their low ability to communicate (Katungi, 2006).

Sourcing of agricultural information and use is along gender lines. Women are more risk averse (Croson and Gneezy, 2008) and perceptions that women are not "real" farmers also limit their access to information sources (Doss, 2001). Male farmers are engaged in more geographically dispersed social networks, thus giving them a greater chance to access information (Haddad and Maluccio, 2003).

Marital status of a farmer influence access to information. Opara (2008) noted that married farmers sought information more due to desire to produce more for family consumption and also for sale. The desire to produce more could lead to agricultural information seeking and use. The size of a household is also a factor that affects agricultural information access and use. Kacharo (2007) asserts that higher number of family members leads to higher exposure to get information.

Agricultural information can only be properly exploited by farmers who have certain levels of formal literacy. Farmers with basic education are more likely to adopt new technology, and become more productive. Education enhances the ability to derive, decode and evaluate useful information for agricultural production (Ani, 1998). According to Gundu (2006), the adaptation and use of new innovation assumes a higher level of literacy. Most farmers in the

developing world are however rural based and are less literate. For instance, in 2008, the adult literacy level in Kenya was 74% (Tilvawala and Myers, 2009). Arokoyo (2005) identified high level of illiteracy as a major constraint to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) utilization by farmers.

Land is one of the most important resources in Kenya as it is the base upon which agriculture activities are carried out (GoK, 2006). Resource endowment is one of the factors affecting farmers' decision to adopt a new agricultural technology (Khan *et al.*, 2008). Land size is often used as an indicator of wealth and proxy for social status and influence. Farmers with large farms are likely to be better informed (Nkonya *et al.*, 1997), richer and more keen in searching for information on improved technologies (Okwu and Iorkaa 2011).

Agricultural production coupled with security of tenure is more reliable and allows for a wider and more diversified cropping patterns as well as production of high value crops. Secure land tenure provides an incentive and authority for farmers to adopt technologies. Lack of secure property rights affects the household investment (Samuel, 2001).

The ability of farmers to adapt technologies requires financing so as to improve production. Earnings from off- farm activities provide ready cash for input purchases as well as other household needs. Lack of access to credit and savings services for farmers in many rural areas, limit their ability to purchase needed technological inputs (Anderson, 1984). Gundu (2006) found that the small holder farmers lack economic capability to access and use relevant information. Off-farm income may be used to compensate for missing and imperfect credit markets (Lamb, 2003). Greater off-farm income means more cash available to the household to invest on-farm (Clay *et al.*, 1998).

Social networks play an important role in information transfer. Farmers observe and learn from others in their network about the suitability and profitability of new agricultural production methods. The networks are particularly important for women, who often have less access to formal dissemination channels (Gundu, 2006). In contrast, men may be engaged in more geographically dispersed social networks, such as community projects, and may participate more in civic engagement (Haddad and Maluccio, 2003). Such participation provides them with greater access to information about agricultural innovations and stimulates information exchange with others (Granovetter, 1973).

Rogers (1995) indicated that the core of technology diffusion consists of interpersonal network of information exchange between those individuals who have already adopted innovation and those who are then influenced to adopt. Together, they assess the worthiness of technologies and suitability to their farming conditions (Minja *et al.*, 2004). Katungi (2006) indicated that social capital is measured by five indicators, each capturing a different aspect of social interaction: the size of the social network, the frequency of interaction in social institutions and civic engagement.

Neelemaghan (1981) pointed out that one of the prerequisites for information use is its accessibility, because farmer's mobility may be limited even basic access to public markets may be limited which constitutes an important place where agricultural information is exchanged (Katungi, 2006).

Agricultural extension has evolved through improvements, development and adoption of more participatory systems. One of the models for technology transfer is Training and Visit (T&V) extension system which was promoted by the World Bank. The system was developed to put the farmer, the resource constraints, abilities and needs at the center of the whole extension effort (Semana, 2002). The high costs of operating the elaborate structures, combined with the lack of new technologies, however led to the abandonment of the model. Few of the classic T&V programs still operate today (Semana, 2002).

The Farmer Field School (FFS) is another approach which was initially developed in Asia in the early 1990s to address a major threat to food security resulting from dramatic yield losses caused by the brown plant hopper. It is an innovative, participatory and interactive learning approach. Farmer Field School is a learner centred approach, whereby farmers through observation, experimentation and evaluation, leading to understanding, are equipped to address challenges and introduce appropriate changes in their farm management practices (Hiller *et al.*, 2009). The field is the primary learning material, and extension workers are facilitators not teachers. Farmers are the main actors in this process and outsiders (extension agents, researchers, Non-Governmental Organizations) take a role as facilitators or resource centres.

Mass media includes electronic such as radio, television and internet and print like newspapers, magazines, posters and extension brochures (Abubakar, 2007). Mass media plays a great role in provision of agricultural information in shortest possible time over a large area (Tadesse, 2008). Djojmartono and Pertini (1998) noted that radio and television

are more appropriate for one-way communication, reaching a lot of people quickly with fairly simple ideas. Radio has been acknowledged as the most important medium for communicating with the rural populations of Sub-Saharan African countries (FAO, 2001).

Lwoga (2010) noted the advancements in the ICTs as an opportunity for developing countries to harness and utilize information and knowledge so as to improve productivity in agriculture. Technological constraints however, such as unstable supply of electricity and the lack of adequate technical support may limit the use of electronics (Melkote and Steeves, 2001).

2.2.1 Dependency and Articulation Theory

The study was informed by the Dependency and Articulation of Modes of Production theories, which were developed within the Marxist school of thought. One of the proponents of the Articulation of modes of production theory was Meillasoux (1981). The dependency theory was also used in this study. The dependency theorists perceive peripheral economies as part of the capitalist world economy. Dependency is a situation where the development in the metropolitan countries is responsible for underdevelopment in the third world countries. The introduction of cash crops in Konoin led to underdevelopment. This made the theory useful for the analysis of this study. The introduction of new crops by Europeans both cash and food crops was a major move towards underdevelopment and dependency, this is because the traditional food crops which had high nutritional value were replaced with new crops that could be easily affected by the unstable world prices due to the marketing systems. In addition, Africa's growing dependence on western technology marked the beginning of external dependency. The Articulation of Modes of Production theory sees the appearance of capitalism either through a process of internal development or as a result of external imposition as leading to a process of more, or less rapid and inevitable disintegration of the pre-capitalist modes of production and the subordination of these modes under capitalist relations of production. The appearance of capital as an independent and leading force in agriculture does not take place at once but gradually in particular lines of production.

Leys, (1994) asserted that the peasants' mode of production was in a sense transitional and that every year that passed, the peasants would tend more and more to become mere aspects of the capitalist mode of production. The establishment of colonial rule resulted in a lot of economic changes. The introduction of money economy, taxation, wage, labour and new

crops was all geared towards the economic change among the Kipsigis who were progressing in their indigenous production systems before colonialism.

This made the articulation of modes of production theory appropriate for the study. A part from keeping animals, they also grew food crops which sustained their food requirements. They had diversified food production, processing and storage systems (Omwoyo, 2004). The colonial period marked the introduction of the capitalist mode of production which slowly began to replace the indigenous mode. The new modes of production slowly modified the indigenous Kipsigis agricultural systems.

This was experienced through the introduction of new crops like maize and tea as a cash crop. The capitalist mode of production began to modify, marginalize, destroy and eventually subordinated the pre-capitalist mode of production (Goodman, 1987). This theory was used in this study to investigate the extent to which the capitalist mode of production got integrated into the pre-capitalist mode of production in Konoin, Bomet County. When tea was introduced into the area, it replaced the traditional crops like wimbieleusine making the Kipsigis to become commodity producers and gradually integrated into the capitalist world economy. As a result of this the Kipsigis started to lose their indigenous system of production and began producing for foreign market which was out of their control (Omwoyo, 2004).

Konoin was one of the areas in Kipsigis land to adopt tea production which has continued to experience tremendous expansion. Some aspects of dependency theory were useful in the analysis of this study. Europeans introduced a cash crop which was labour-intensive and hence ways of recruiting labourers had to be devised. This led to all men being coerced into wage labour either by reason of taxation or force. As a result of this, Kipsigis households suffered severely from insufficient labour leading to food shortages. This means that introduction of estate tea production severely affected food crop production among the Kipsigis. In essence the introduction of tea was a step towards dependency among the Kipsigis of Konoin Bomet County as they totally became dependent on tea production at the expense of any other economic activities. The articulation of modes of production was also useful in explaining this scenario as well.

2.2.2 Empirical Review

Katungi (2006) studied the effective factors influencing the tea farming production in African Country. In his study confirmed that there are various factors affecting tea farming in African countries such as:

1. Constraints of inputs

The five main causes that lead to low use of agriculture input include the country's geographical structure, insufficient inputs stocks, affordability, farmer's knowledge and skills and incentives. As in the case of geographical structure more than 39% of the cultivated land is on slope which in turn occupies over 25% of available land in Rwanda. This not only increase the risk of soil erosion but also limits the use of tractors in agricultural activities, for example in 2003, Kenya had 50 times more than tractors per hectore. Another issue is insufficient national stocks; Rwanda has for long time lacked indigenous sources of fertilizers and pesticides. Affordability is a problem because of lack of domestic sources of fertilizers and high cost of pesticides; while most farmers are poor and lack of access to credits to finance inputs. Farmers 'knowledge and skills are limited though a number of farmers understand the fact that better use of inputs could improve the yield.

2. Costs effective Management

Farmers are not able to keep records of their production expenses including their own labor and that of their families; inputs that are traditionally not regarded as costs by most farmers. Therefore, they are not able to maximize the benefits of their investments and remain poor despite all their hard work. The smallholder farmers usually they first grow the crops then look for markets. This often leads to a glut in the market and the farmers are forced to sell their produce at markedly lower prices than their production costs. Obviously this results in huge losses for them. Farmers 'incentives are not defined so there is always no clear link between price and quality (IPAR, 2009).

3. Vulnerability to weather related shocks

Lack of irrigation and weak meteorological capacity are major causes of high vulnerability to weather related shocks of Rwanda agriculture sector. The cost of irrigation is high, especially at the hillside. Weak meteorological capacity is also a big challenge. In Rwanda there is lack of adequate meteorological equipment and reliable weather forecasting increase uncertainty of farming activities (IPAR, 2009)

4. Markets

The two factors are underlying the low commercialization of agriculture products are inadequate of business skills and entrepreneurial ethic and quality produce. Lack of business skills and entrepreneurship is also a problem since; there is very limited agribusiness entrepreneurship in Rwanda. Key underlying factors include among others lack of detailed business plan, lack of understanding by banks, lack of information about opportunities, reluctance to use banking services.

Low quality produce is an issue of concern, with most production intended for own-family consumption; crop farmers have weak incentives to increase quality. Lack of sustainable market and post-harvest management remained top challenges for the farmers. In addition quality standard and process, which are key determination of competitiveness on international market, may be poorly understood by many farmers (PSF, 2008).

5. Value addition

The Rwandan agriculture sub-sectors have high but unrealized potential for the value addition. This is due to lack of access to credit facilities, poor rural infrastructure and weak land title. Agriculture has traditionally been seen as a risk investment by banks, rural infrastructure is poor, due to in availability of adequate energy and water resources, and this is that processing facilities often run below capacity. Besides that, poor qualities of roads; this raises transport costs and waste time to the market. Fragment poorly defined land ownership makes it difficult to buy and sell land and creates risk to investors (PSF, 2008).

6. Exportation

Two major issues make it difficult for Rwanda product to penetrate the international market; they are both transport costs and lack of marketing. Because many producers lack specialist marketing skills and the small domestic market, farmers may routinely come into contact with customers limiting their ability to develop this expertise (World Bank 2007).

2.3 THE EFFECTIVE INDICATORS OF WELFARE OF TEA FARMERS

Various studies have been conducted around the globe to establish the determinants of saving among various groups of people. A study by Lahiri (1989) of some Asian countries reported that the rate of growth of personal disposable income determines private savings. An investigation by Kibet, Mutai, Ouma, Ouma and Owuor (2009) reported that savings among small holder farmers, entrepreneurs and teachers in rural Kenya is determined by the type of occupation, household income, age, gender of household head, education, dependency ratio, service charges for accessing financial services, transportation cost and access to credit. Oliveira and others, 1998

(as cited in Akpan et al, 2011) found that income, physical wealth, household size, education and age of household head as the determinants of financial savings in rural Mozambique. A study by Akpan et al (2011) reveals that tax, income, education, family size and membership of a social group influence saving attitude of workers.

A survey conducted by Selhausen (2011) on Mpanga Tea growers found a relatively low savings culture among Mpanga's tea growers. It was noted that tea growers save to protect themselves from unpredictable emergencies such as sickness, natural disaster, burials and plan for the future

to acquire assets. On the other hand saving was observed to be higher during peak seasons.

The

survey observed the following as factors that contributed to a low savings culture among Mpanga tea farmers; firstly, individuals preferred saving in local groups or other Saccos because distance

from their homes to the Sacco posed as a barrier. The second factor was lack of money. This was due to the fact that some earned too little to save and others did not have enough money to save. The thirdly, distance between the Mpanga factory and respondent's tea centres attracts high financial costs in terms of transport and lost time.

Tea farmers in Kenya comprise of large and small scale farmers. The large scale farmers occupy the vast majority of land and produce huge volumes of tea. They comprise of the big multinationals, private and government factories. The large scale farmers rely on small scale farmers to meet their production needs. The small scale farmers are categorized in groups of

self-delivery and outreach farmers. The self-delivery farmers pluck, weigh, manage and deliver the green leaf to their assigned tea factories directly while the outreach farmers are collected in groups also known as zones and are allocated tea collection centres where they deliver their tea and the large scale farmers collect from there.

Income is considered as an important factor in the determination of the saving behaviour of an individual (Gedela, 2012). The Keynesian theory of 1936 identified disposable income as an important determinant of saving. A survey on Mpanga tea growers by Selhausen (2011) indicates that some farmers fail to save because they do not have enough money to save or their income is too little to allow them to set aside money for saving purposes. In the research conducted by Athukorala and Sen (2001) on determinants of private saving in India found that savings rate of households rose with the growth rate and level of disposable income. Chowa et al (2012) in their study on determinants of saving among low-income individuals in rural Uganda their findings were consistent with neoclassical theory which states that when people have more disposable income they save more.

The LCH suggests that there exists a relationship between age and savings rate. Burney and Khan (1992) found that savings increase with age crossing a certain limit. Gedela (2012) in his study on determinants of saving behaviour in rural households found a positive relationship between age of the household head and savings where increase in age resulted in increase in saving but as the household head becomes old the savings start declining. The gender of the household heads in most studies has shown to have an impact on the level of saving. A study conducted by Lihuku (2006) revealed that households that were headed by males saved a lot more than female headed households because the females are usually required to share their time between activities that increase the income of the household and housekeeping..

Access to credit is another determinant of saving which is observed by various studies to have a negative effect on saving. Kibet et al (2009) in their study noted that among low income households saving is usually done for consumption purposes and is rarely converted to investments. They further observed that credit constraint encourages households to save

while

improved access to credit results in reduced saving and relatively less increase in investment expenditure by the households in the short run. A study conducted by Cronje (2010) draws lessons from China where the financial services sector is under developed leading to credit constraint a factor which contributes to high levels of household saving. Households in China are forced to save in order to purchase big items such as houses and cars which are investment expenditures.

In a study conducted by Akpan et al (2011), in Nigeria on determinants of saving among Agrobased firm workers indicate that tax has a negative effect influence on savings of agro based workers. The study goes on to notice that as tax rate increases the permanent income according to the permanent income hypothesis by Friedman will reduce, thereby resulting in the reduction of transitory income which in return lowers the ability to save by the workers. The study notes that as tax rate increases, it lowers the aggregate disposable income resulting in an increase in the consumption expenditure of households and a corresponding decrease in savings.

2.3.1 Neoclassical economic theory

The neoclassical economic theory of saving, The two main theories anchoring the concept of saving are the Life-Cycle Hypothesis and Permanent Income Hypothesis. The Lifecycle Hypothesis advanced by Modigliani and Richard Brumberg and Permanent Income Hypothesis advanced by Friedman. According to Chohan, Masa and Ansong (2012) the two theories assume that households are concerned about long term consumption opportunities and therefore explain savings and consumption in terms of expected future income. The two theories assume that savings is a way of smoothing out consumption in the face of income fluctuations.

The Life Cycle hypotheses' advanced by Ando and Modigliani, (1963), Modigliani and Brumberg (1954), view the primary motive of saving as future consumption that is to meet expenses after retirement and acquire wealth. The model is built around the consumption and saving behaviour of an individual who is assumed to maximize the present value of life time utility, subject to budget constraint. Modigliani refers to the analysis of consumption and saving patterns and implies that constrained individuals consume a constant percentage of the present value of their lifetime income due the consumption smoothing motive. It implies

that individuals both plan their consumption and savings behaviour over the long term and intend to even out their consumption in the best possible manner over their entire lifetime. Hence people consume less than their economic resources to enable them save for a future rainy day.

According to the LCH model, with fluctuations in income over a course of a person's life, saving behaviour is determined by one's stage in the life cycle. Change in age is seen as playing a vital role on spending and saving decisions. Individuals who smoothen their consumption over their lifetime are net savers during their working years and don't save during retirement. The middle aged becomes conscious net savers because they plan for their life after retirement.

The Permanent income Hypothesis by Friedman (1957) stresses the fact that consumption is proportional to an individual's estimation of his or her permanent income hence people base their spending decisions on expectations of permanent income. Friedman describes permanent income as the average income that people can earn over their life time. He also makes a distinction between transitory income and permanent income where transitory income is viewed as windfall gain or income. Changes in transitory income are believed not have an effect on spending and saving decisions but shifts in permanent income would be important in shaping spending levels. Individual's consumption is adjusted based on their perception of permanent income over their life time. When the permanent income changes their consumption patterns responds accordingly.

The concern about long term permanent income for consumption is the main motivating factor to save.

The two theories assume that human beings are logical in their views or feel about the future as such they balance their present spending according to the effect it will have on their income levels. They consciously spend their resources in a manner that does not have a negative impact on the resources that they rely on to assist them in the future. In the process of deciding on whether to spend or not intervening variables such as income level, age, education, and various financial commitments emerges to play a role in determining an individual's action to save.

2.3.2 Empirical Review

Gedela (2012) studies the contribution factors of household welfare in Africa. He observes that most households in developing countries are poor, risk averse and operate in scenarios of uncertainty and imperfect financial markets hence the above theories are deficient in explaining the saving behaviour of such households. The effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers provide a background to understanding the health scenario in a country. This section on the indicators welfare of tea farmers provides data on education, gender, poverty, housing, amenities, employment and other economic indicators. These indicators for the country as well as states help in identifying the linkages between socio-economic indicators and achievement of health goals.

1. Increase of income and Savings

Savings refers to the liquidity depository in a bank in order to expand their deepen outreach and help householders to increase their welfare and their new investments (Carey, 1998). Income is money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service or through investing capital. Income is consumed to fuel day-to-day expenditures. Most people age 65 and under receive the majority of their income from a salary or wages earned from a job. Investments, pensions and Social Security are primary sources of income for retirees. In businesses, income can refer to a company's remaining revenues after all expenses and taxes have been paid. In this case, it is also known as "earnings". Most forms of income are subject to taxation (Gedela, 2012)

2. Increase households Income

Income generation interventions attempt to address poverty, unemployment, and lack of economic opportunities to increase participants' ability to generate income and secure livelihoods. These interventions can take a wide variety of forms, including microcredit programs that provide small loans to individuals or groups who would not normally qualify for loans from conventional financial institutions. Microcredit is one form of microfinance, which involves the provision of a wider range of financial services, such as access to savings, credit, and insurance to poor people. It is the process by which a company markets and sells a product or service to produce income

3. Health Care and Insurance

Health care or healthcare is the maintenance or improvement of health via the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease, illness, injury, and other physical and mental

impairments in human beings. It funds and administers Medicare, the national medical insurance scheme; supplies pharmaceutical benefits; funds public hospitals and population health programs (with the states and territories); regulates much of the health system, including private health insurance, pharmaceuticals, and medical services; and has the main funding and regulatory responsibility for government-subsidized residential care facilities

5. Access to Education

Education is important in life because it gives people the skills and tools they need to navigate the world. Without education, people would not be able to read, write, calculate or communicate; they would also not be able to perform jobs competently, accurately and safely. Education also teaches people about the world in which they live, including information about history, philosophy and culture.

Education is as the act or process of imparting or acquiring general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning and judgment, and generally of preparing oneself or others intellectually for mature life. Literacy knows how to read and write. Education is to be able to reason, to use your ability to read and write to your benefit and to be able to gain your spectrum of knowledge by trying to surge deeper into the literate knowledge imparted to you (Gedela, 2012)

6. Having shelter and Housing

It is universally accepted that housing is the second most important need of man after food. Housing transcends shelter and thus comprises of the facilities and other social services within the environment which links man with his remote and immediate neighborhood. Good-quality housing is a key element for ensuring a healthy village. Poor housing can lead to many health problems, and is associated with infectious diseases, stress and depression. Everyone should therefore have access to good-quality housing and a pleasant home environment that makes them happy and content

7. Food Satisfaction

Food Security is one of major elements of development and poverty alleviation and has been the goal of many international and national public organizations. This widely accepted definition points to the following dimensions of food security: Food availability: the availability of sufficient quantities of food of appropriate quality, supplied through domestic production or imports (including food aid).

Food access: access by individuals to adequate resources (entitlements) for acquiring appropriate foods for a nutritious diet. Entitlements are defined as the set of all commodity bundles over which a person can establish command given the legal, political, economic and social arrangements of the community in which they live (including traditional rights such as access to common resources) (Gedela, 2012).

7. Creation of new business

Innovation means creativity aiming at increasing production in the enterprise. The innovation is made through the decision of the entrepreneur himself or his/her manager (Tayebwa, 1998). Business growth refers to the increased assets which ensure a more equitable of income distribution and wealth. However tea farmers' welfare is supported by Government Support Policies including the Policies by central government; provincial government; local governments. Policies including Tax reduction: VAT reduction; Subsidies: direct subsidies and input subsidies; Financial support to tea growers and companies; R&D and extension/training; Support to cooperatives (mainly tax reduction benefit); and Market information (Gedela, 2012).

Ogot and Ochieng (1995) historical study observed that Post independent Africa kept increasing its cash crop production to earn foreign exchange. Transport, infrastructure and technical assistance have been directed towards reviving cash crops. As Africa has invested more heavily on cash crops, per capital food production has declined. They noted that even during drought, some African countries managed to increase their total harvest of cash crop. The reasons given include the value of cash crops as compared to other crops. This value is in terms of money earned through the sale of these crops and change living condition of citizens in that area.

2.4 THE TEA FARMING AND WELFARE OF TEA FARMERS

The study has shown that a large number of tea farmers live below the poverty line based solely on the tea income. The study confirms the results of a previous survey on the welfare monitoring undertaken by Kenyan government (CBS, 2003). The variations between the two studies on the proportion of population living below the poverty line are associated with the time factor and the fact that this study restricted itself to welfare based on tea income. The later study has provided a clear picture of farmers' welfare based on the leading export crop with a history of the well-organized institutions that are envied by other crops' enterprises.

The challenge of addressing poverty and improving returns to such an enterprise is colossal, unlike in other enterprises that target to emulate this particular industry in terms of smallholder organization, value-additions, inputs credit and distribution systems, information dissemination and modes and timeliness of paying farmers (Gesimba et al., 2005) and marketing functions implementations (Muturi et al., 2001)

The analysis has shown that a number of avenues exist in improving farmers' welfare by targeting maximizations of returns from tea enterprise. The factors that may be targeted for improved returns of tea enterprise include improved tea productivity, population control interventions and improved green leaf tea prices. By tea growers increasing the levels of investment on their tea farms they will achieve high productivity that will improve their welfare. Another factor, which may not be applicable everywhere due to limitation of land resource, is increasing acreage under tea.

Tea farm productivity could be addressed through adoptions of high yielding cultivars and routine tea management practices. Other factors, which will immensely increase yields, is recommendations of the optimal spacing for various tea types. Already varied spacing regimes that range from having 5383 to 18150 tea bushes per hectare exists with the paucity of justification for such wide variations. Targeting information to the demand areas will improve extension impact as tea is a perennial crop and a mistake undertaken within a specific time may not be ameliorated without farmers reinvesting in high costs operations. By targeting farmers who would wish to plant tea on the right variety, spacing and land preparation, efficiency in production will be achieved as land utilization would be optimal and cases of Armillaria root rot, (a fungal diseases affecting tea) will be controlled (Otieno, 2002).

Efficiency in tea processing, transportation and human resource management will save cost that will be paid to farmers as increased green leaf prices. Improved marketing system for tea through branding, value additions and diversification of markets will ensure better returns to the farmers. Although the auction tea marketing system has been perceived to serve the industry well, efforts to diversify to more competitive markets (Sabur et al., 2000) need to be considered. Implementation of a value chain analysis of the entire industry activities from research and development, to raw material supply and production, to transport and delivery, would aid in establishing specific areas for interventions in upgrading to enhance profitability.

2.4.1 A Modified Cost-Return Model

A modified cost-return model was used to establish the net welfare or return from tea enterprises after tea related management costs and those for up-keeping the households above the poverty line were deducted from total earnings. Since the study aimed at establishing the well-being of tea farmers, and determines the intervention strategies of improving tea growers returns based on the contributory factors to poverty or well-being, it was assumed that farmers rely entirely on tea for their livelihood.

A tea farming household was considered to be poor if returns from tea enterprise were less than its financial requirement to meet basic needs. Household financial requirements were based on the number of adult equivalent and the cost of buying basket of necessities. The annual cost of basic basket that allows minimum nutritional requirements to be met at 2250 calories per adult equivalent per day in addition to the cost of meeting basic non-food needs. This amount is set at Kenya Shillings 14868 per annum (CBS, 2003). The welfare level was net of return from tea enterprise (tea income less operation costs of tea framing) minus the household costs of basic necessities. A positive results indicated household able to meet basic requirements and hence above the poverty line. A negative sum indicated household requirements outstripped returns and hence the household was unable to meet the minimum survival necessities and hence members were considered to be living below the poverty line.

2.4.2 Empirical Review

Chepkemoi Kirui F., (2017) the effects of smallholder tea production in kenya: the case of bomet county, 1954–2002. Tea is grown in estates mostly owned by multinational companies and smallholder tea producers. This study investigated how smallholder tea production effects in welfare of citizens in Konoin, Bomet County in the period 1954 - 2002. The objectives of the study were: To investigate the factors that led to the introduction of tea growing in Konoin, Bomet County; To analyse the effects of smallholder tea production on food crop production and to examine the role of KTDA on the expansion of Smallholder tea production in Konoin, Bomet County from 1954 to 2002. The study was informed by two theories: The Dependency theory and The Articulation of Modes of Production theory. Purposive sampling technique was used to identify the informants with vital information. These included the people who witnessed the introduction of tea growing in Konoin Bomet County.

The research tools for the study were interview schedule and observation schedule. Data was collected from farmers, and those practicing tea related activities sampled from the study area. Data analysis entailed corroboration of secondary data with primary data. Finally, data was presented qualitatively. The study established that smallholder tea production impacted adversely on food production as too much land was put under cash crops production. This, therefore made people to rely on the market for purchase of food hence their living standards was compromised. KTDA was also found to have had a positive impact in the development and expansion of smallholder tea production in Konoin, Bomet County.

Odhiambo and Hezron (2004) and Kabura (2005) observed that declining living standards and poverty was evident among many rural families in Murang'a that for a long time depended on cash crops as a major source of income. What farmers earned from cash crops such as tea declined due to competition in the global market and changes in consumer's tastes among other factors. At the same time, population brought conditions of large family sizes and small farm sizes which impacted negatively on food production. Odhiambo (2004) further observed that there was overuse of available land which coupled with drastic changes in climatic conditions led to poor agricultural performance leading to hunger and poverty. The ideas of these researchers were useful to this research. They showed how family size and farm sizes had contributed to a reduction of land under food crop production leading to food insecurity. The study focused on Muranga while this study focused on Konoin, Bomet County between 1954 and 2002.

2.5 CRITICAL REVIEW

According to the studies of Katungi (2006) on the effective factors influencing the tea farming production in African Country; Gedela (2012) who studies the contribution factors of household welfare in Africa; Ogot and Ochieng (1995) historical study observed that Post independent Africa kept increasing its cash crop production to earn foreign exchange; Chepkemoi Kirui F., (2017) the effects of smallholder tea production in kenya: the case of bomet county, 1954–2002; and Odhiambo and Hezron (2004) and Kabura (2005) observed that declining living standards and poverty was evident among many rural families in Murang'a that for a long time depended on cash crops as a major source of income.

They are all contributing some ideas for literature but these studies did not evaluate the tea farmers' welfare for Rwanda as gap left. Therefore, to complete this gap, the study attempts to find out how does effectiveness of tea farming influence the tea farmer's welfare in

Rwanda especially COPTHE SHAGASHA's members by establishing the relationship between the two variables doing correlation coefficient test on basis to computer software of SPSS version 20.0.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.0 INTRODUCTION

This section aims at presenting the methodology was used in the course of conducting research, it narrates various aspects such as the research design, source of data, the population under the study, sample size, sampling techniques, data collection instruments, methods of data analysis, ethical consideration, and the limitation of the study.

3.1 RESEARCH APPROACH AND DESIGN

This research is non-experimental research where it applied qualitative and quantitative approaches and descriptive and correlation research designs. It is descriptive where describing the influential factors of tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA, and describing also indicators of welfare of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This research adopted the correlation as it looks for relationship between tea farming and tea farmers' welfare by using SPSS version 20.0

3.2 TARGET POPULATION

Jarol B., and Richard C., (1995) defined a population as any group of people, organizations, objects, or events about which you want to draw conclusions. In this research, target population included the members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA as estimated on rate of 325 members.

3.3 SAMPLING PROCEDURES

In this study the use of convenience sampling technique was applied where researcher chose to select sample after convincing members from COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This sampling technique was used to select 74 respondents who are best met with research objectives

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE

Manheim, and Rih, R.C (1996), define a sample as a small group attained of cases drawn from organization and used to represent some large group. In other words, it is a subset from a larger population. To obtain good quality of data and ensure that there is no bias in the data collection, the researcher used the formula of Cochran (1963:75) in sampling proportions.

$$n = \frac{No}{1 + \left(\frac{No-1}{N}\right)} \text{ Where, } n_0 = \frac{Z^2 * p * q}{d^2}$$

Where: **n**= Sample size, **N**= Size of the population, **No**: indefinite universe, **Z_α**= t-student distribution, **p**=probability of success, **q**=probability of failure, **d**= margin error.

For Cochran, the margin error varies between 5% and 10%. During this research, the margin error of 10% is applied, and then the confidence level is 90%, our probability of success is p=.5, and the probability of failure is q=.5, as Z_α=1.96

$$n_0 = \frac{1.96^2 * 0.5 * 0.5}{0.1^2} = 96.04 \approx 96 \quad n = \frac{96}{1 + \left(\frac{96-1}{325}\right)} = 74.28 \approx 74$$

Then the sample size (n) of this research is 74 respondents from target population of COPTHE.

3.5 Research Instruments for Data collection

The data collected during this study are in primary data and secondary data.

3.5.1 Primary data

Questionnaire

In this study, the questionnaires were presented in closed ended questions and addressed to the respondents from COPTHE SHAGASHA for writing their opinions. The questionnaire distribution protocol in the “COPTHE SHAGASHA” as tea cooperative organized in a way that facilitates the process of collecting data.

The questionnaire that the researcher asks, it was composed by four parts, where part one is questions related to the respondents profile, the second part was related to effectiveness of tea farming; the third part is relating to indicators of tea farmers’ welfare; and the fourth part is the perception of respondents on the influence of tea farming on the tea farmers’ welfare.

Observation

In participating to the field of research, the researcher observed the situations that happen in at COPTHE SHAGASHA and getting the image and conditions in which effectiveness of tea farming influences welfare of their members.

3.5.2 Secondary Data

Documentary technique

In respect of secondary data, the researcher used the documentary technique. The researcher read the reports and publication journal about tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA and its contribution to welfare of members.

3.6 ETHICAL ISSUES

In this research, a researcher considered the sources of data in both primary and secondary data. In order to collect such data, the researcher follows right protocols where a letter requesting permission to collect data from respondents of COOPTHE SHAGASHA was delivered by the Dean of faculty. Before any contact with respondents gentle and polite presentation and introduction was made. Enough time to respond was given to the respondents and they were assured about confidentiality.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

In this research, processing data was concerned with putting the responses into meaningful categories where it consisted with editing, coding, classifying and tabulation.

Editing: is focusing to the process of going through questionnaire to ensure that the errors and omission are corrected. Editing in this research involved the inspection and if necessary, connections of each questionnaire or observation form; the basic purpose of editing is to impose some minimum quality standards on the raw data.

Coding: a researcher coded in the procedure by which data was categorized. Through coding, the raw data was transformed into symbols usually numerals that may be tabulated and counted. The transformation is not automatic; however, involved judgment on the part of coder.

Recording: the obtained data from respondents of COOPTHE SHAGASHA was entered into computer to be analyzed

Classifying: the answers acquired, coded and tallies were used to determine the frequencies of each response. Similar responses would be grouped according to their different categories.

Tabulation: refers to the part of technical process on statistical analysis of data that involves counting to determine the number cases that fall into various categories. Thus after eliminating errors, codes are assigned to each answer. This stage led to the construction of statistical tables showing frequency distribution of answers to questions address to respondents.

The methods were used to analyze the data in this research was done in accordance of SPSS where Descriptive Statistical method was applied to describe the frequencies, percentages, and cumulative percentages of data on influential factors of tea farming and indicators of tea farmers' welfare. The correlation coefficient method was calculated to show the relationship between the two variables was shown in this research.

3.8 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY MEASURES

Validity of Instruments

Validity was concerned with the way in which we value the information from analysis and take into account what researcher observed. It is found that every item has meaningful. Besides, validity of the research outcomes refers to extent to which what is observed reflects what is expected. To reach on that, researcher consulted first of all to the experts in research methodology for helping him to correct the language errors and give him the manner of asking the research questions. However, supervisor also was among to the experts consulted.

Reliability of Instruments

In this research, researcher distributed the sample seven questionnaires to COOPAC Ltd for pre-testing the result before going at COOPTHE SHAGASHAas field of this research. So, the result from pre-test at COOPAC referred to Cronbanch's Alpha of 0.75. During the pre-test of sample questionnaire the result obtained is indicated in the below table.

Table 3.1: Legend of Cronbach' s Test of Reliability

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable (Surveys)
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Table 3.2: Reliability Statistics from pre-test done at COOPAC Ltd

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.758	.772	9

Source: Pre-test of reliability 2018

The pre-test result done at COOPAC Ltd shows the reliability statistics of 0.758 (e.g: 75.8%) which categorized on $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$ as acceptable (Surveys) questionnaire; this allows the researcher to continue with the study at COOPTHE as case study.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION, AND SUMMARY

4.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the findings from respondents selected at COOPTHE SHAGASHA in relation to effectiveness of tea farming for the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda. Therefore the data are presented quantitatively and qualitatively on basis to research objectives mainly using computer software specifically Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 20.0). The objectives under investigated were to find out the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA; to assess the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, and to determine the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.1 PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATIONS

During this study at COOPTHE SHAGASHA, questionnaires were distributed to the 74 respondents selected from members of this agriculture cooperative, and they were given one week and two days of responding to the questions. The participation rate was 100.0% of responding, and this helps the researcher to continue with editing, coding, recording, classifying and make statistical tables. The analysis of this study shows the respondents' profile, the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA; effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, and the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.1.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

This section illustrates the profile of respondents included by ages, gender, education level, marital status, and experience in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Age of Respondents

Age is the time during which a person or animal has lived, or time during which a thing has existed. It is found that the average age of people in the workforce is getting higher, with increasing numbers of middle-aged and older workers employed in many different jobs. Thus, it is important to know whether cooperative performance is higher or lower for older workers in comparison with younger workers. Concerning to the ages of respondents during this study at COOPTHE SHAGASHA, the table

4.1 present the data as follows:

Table 4.3: Distribution by age of respondents

Age of respondents	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
19 - 35 years	23	31.1	31.1
36 - 45years	27	36.5	67.6
Valid 45 - 65 years	19	25.7	93.2
Above 65 years	5	6.8	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.1 presents the distribution of respondents by age in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Out of 100.0% of respondents, 31.1% of respondents have ages between 19-35 years; 36.5% respondents are aged between 36-45years; 25.7% respondents have the ages from 45-65 years, while, minority of 6.8% of respondents have been above 65 years. COOPTHE SHAGASHA members are mature, productive people who know what to do towards to enhance their welfare.

According to Oribabor, P., E., (2000) confirmed that age initiatives recruit stakeholders across many sectors, including municipal planning, public health, arts and culture, parks and recreation, government, business, housing, the faith community, environment, technology, health care, and grassroots organizations. Traditionally, many programs for older adults fall within the purview of the aging services sector, but successful age-friendly programs generally operate both in and beyond those agencies and service providers. However, to build long-term sustainable Cooperative for members, the age must engage across sectors and learn about community needs and initiatives that serve all ages.

Gender of Respondents

Gender is the range of characteristics pertaining to, and differentiating between masculinity and femininity. There is an influence of gender to the achievement of goals and performance of cooperative as indicated by respondents met in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The information contents on table 4.2 show gender distribution of respondents in COOPTHE SHAGASHA as follows.

Table 4.4: Distribution by Gender of Respondents

Gender of Respondents	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	47	63.5	63.5
Valid Female	27	36.5	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.2 presented above shows that the respondents of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were both male and female. The findings indicated that the 63.5% respondents were males, while 36.5% of respondents were females in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Hence, the Rwandan gender law expected 30% of gender balance in the Cooperative opportunity. This helps the researcher to make the confidence on the data from both sexes (female and male) respondents of COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Maria Nieves R., (2003) confirmed that gender, influence the sustainability of Cooperative development. It maintains that the discrimination that affects women is expressed in our societies mainly through the division of labour by sex, with the result that responsibility for household work and bringing up children devolves almost exclusively upon women; inequality between men and women in terms of access to productive resources and the benefits of these; limitations on participation in decision making processes and access to the various forms of public power.

However, increasing knowledge about the ways in which women in different groups and sectors of society participate in cooperative development has highlighted the interconnection between gender, the environment and sustainability. In the transition towards the goal of sustainability, women have emerged as a force, not only in support of proper environmental management, but also in demands for better quality of life and greater social equity.

Education of respondents

Education is the formal learning which is typically divided into a number of educational stages covering early childhood education, primary education, secondary education and tertiary (or higher) education. To have educated people in the members of Cooperative lead to its sustainability and stimulate their welfare. The findings shown in the table 4.3 illustrates data on education level of members by COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.5: Distribution by Level of Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Masters and above	2	2.7	2.7
Bachelors' degree	15	20.3	23.0
Valid Secondary level	31	41.9	64.9
Primary level	26	35.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.3 shows the distribution by education level of respondents from COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Among the 74 of respondent participants during this study, there is no illiterate, where 41.9% of respondents had secondary level; 20.3% of respondents had Bachelors' degree; 2.7% respondents had Masters and above, and 35.1% of respondents had Primary level. COOPTHE SHAGASHA has the educated and qualified members as factor could lead to enhance the welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Koroit, Eunice, (2013) said the success of Cooperative activities has improved due to people having basic knowledge in the affairs of the cooperative. Therefore, it is important to know that almost 100% of the people have formal and informal education that indicates that people knows how to manage their own activities in agriculture. The cooperative can survive and can be sustained for increase welfare of members of Cooperative. The capacity building as a process that helps cooperative enhances its mission, strategy, skills, systems, infrastructure, and human resources to better serve community needs from the cooperative sustainability.

Marital Status of Respondents

Civil status or marital status is any of several distinct options that describe a person's relationship with a significant other. Married, single, divorced, and widowed are examples of civil status. These have any impact on the Cooperative sustainability which is leading channel of welfare of members. In regard of marital status, the table 4.4 presents the findings as follows

Table 4.6: Distribution by Marital status of Respondents

Marital status of Respondents	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	23	31.1	31.1
Married	41	55.4	86.5
Valid Widowed	7	9.5	95.9
Divorced	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.4 shows the distribution of respondent by marital status in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Out of 100.0% respondents who participated during this study, 55.4% of respondents were married; 31.1% respondents were the single; 9.5% of respondents were widow(er), while 4.1% respondents were separated (divorced) respondents from members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Majority of respondents were married, and this category of people was stable to work with COOPTHE SHAGASHA where it helps its members achieving its welfare. Nyiransabimana, A., (2017) argued that marital status influences Cooperative to enhance the welfare of members. This was confirmed by the findings from PAIRB targeted especially married and widowed because their living conditions were worse than the others.

Experience of Respondents

Experience is as the process of doing and seeing things and having things happen to you, or skill or knowledge that you get by doing something. It is the length of time has spent doing something. However, experience of members in the cooperative is among the factors that affect their living conditions. In regard to the experience of members in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, the table 4.5 presents the data as follows.

Table 4.7: Distribution by Experiences of Members in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Experiences in COOPTHE	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1 year	6	8.1	8.1
1 to 2 years	16	21.6	29.7
2 to 3 years	17	23.0	52.7
Valid 3 to 4 years	15	20.3	73.0
4 to 5 years	11	14.9	87.8
5 years and above	9	12.2	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.5 shows the respondents' experiences at COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Out of 74 respondents, the 8.1% of respondents had less than 1year of experience in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 21.6% of respondents are between 1-2years of experience in agriculture at COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 23.0% respondents had the experience between 2 to 3 years of experiences; 20.3% respondents have experience between 3 to 4 years; 14.9% respondents have experience in COOPTHE SHAGASHA from 4 to 5 years; and 12.2% respondents have the experiences on 5 years and above working with COOPTHE SHAGASHA. During this research, it was found that the respondents members had enough experience in agriculture cooperative where the majority have more than 2years of experience in working in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Perry, J., and Paarlberg, L., (2006) argued that experience of members cooperative foster and sustain effectively their activities; it must be both viable and well-managed. Regardless of how imaginative a cooperative's design be, its effectiveness is largely dependent on a variety of other factors, including the skill, experience of agriculture in implementing the activities of cooperative, its financial viability, its capacity to establish effective quality controls, its ability to measure members performance, its skill in creating partnerships and mobilizing volunteers and resources for its activities, and its ability to provide various forms of administrative support help to achieve its welfare in cooperative.

4.1.2 The influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA

According to Katungi (2006) argued that there are many effective factors influencing the tea farming production. In his study confirmed that the factors affecting tea farming in African countries especially in Rwanda are type of tea plant, and the health; care and experience of the farmers; the composition of the soil; farm management; climate in which the tea plants; the knowledge, and skill employed; the growing and processing; the distribution process; and market availability for agriculture cooperative like COOPTHE SHAGASHA as tables below indicated.

Table 4.8: Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the Health of the plan

Type of tea plant, and the health	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	27	36.5	36.5
Agree	34	45.9	82.4
Undecided	5	6.8	89.2
Disagree	5	6.8	95.9
Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.6 illustrates the perceptions of respondents on Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan. Majority of 82.4% respondents included by Strongly Agree and agreed respondents confirmed that Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan. Only 10.9 % respondent included by disagree and strongly disagree respondents refused the idea about Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan. Undecided respondents were 6.8% respondents who did not want to communicate anything about Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan. Generally, more than 82.4% of respondents confirmed that Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan.

Table 4.9: Care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming at COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Care and experience of the farmers'	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	42	56.8	56.8
Agree	18	24.3	81.1
Undecided	5	6.8	87.8
Disagree	6	8.1	95.9
Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.7 presents the perceptions of respondents about Care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*. Among of 100.0% respondents' participants in this study at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*, more than 81.1% of respondents who included by strongly agree and agreed respondents confirmed that Care and experience of the farmers influences the tea farming at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*. Only 12.2 % of respondent included by disagree and strongly disagree respondents refused Care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*; 6.8% respondents' undecided about Care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*. More than 81.1% of respondents confirmed that care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming in *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*.

Table 4.10: The composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming

Composition of the soil	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	28	37.8	37.8
Agree	30	40.5	78.4
Valid Undecided	7	9.5	87.8
Disagree	6	8.1	95.9
Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.8 presents the perceptions of respondents on the composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming. Out of 100.0% respondents in this study at *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*, more than 78.4% of respondents confirmed that the composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming. The 12.2 % of respondent disagreed that composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming; and only 6.8% respondents have been undecided that composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming. Generally more than 78.4% of respondents confirmed that the composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming in *COOPTHE SHAGASHA*.

Table 4.11: Farm Management affect tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA' members

Farm Management affect tea farming	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	33	44.6	44.6
Agree	29	39.2	83.8
Valid Undecided	6	8.1	91.9
Disagree	4	5.4	97.3
Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.9 shows the perceptions of respondents on the farm Management affect tea farming for *COOPTHE SHAGASHA'* members in Shagasha where 83.8% of respondents confirmed that Farm Management affect tea farming for *COOPTHE SHAGASHA'* members in Shagasha; 8.1 % of respondent refused that Farm Management affect tea farming for *COOPTHE SHAGASHA'* members and only 6.8% respondents have been undecided that Farm Management affect tea farming for *COOPTHE SHAGASHA'* members in Shagasha. More than 83.8% respondents confirmed Farm Management affect tea farming for *COOPTHE SHAGASHA'* members

Table 4.12: The climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The climate in which the tea plants growing	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	36	48.6	48.6
Agree	30	40.5	89.2
Valid Undecided	3	4.1	93.2
Disagree	3	4.1	97.3
Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.10 provides the information on the perceptions of respondents about climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in *COOPTHE SHAGASHA* where 89.2% of respondents confirmed that climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea

farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 6.8 % of respondent did not agree with the idea said that the climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and 4.1% respondents have been undecided that the climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 89.2% respondents confirmed climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.13: The knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	29	39.2	39.2
	Agree	27	36.5	75.7
	Undecided	7	9.5	85.1
	Disagree	6	8.1	93.2
	Strongly Disagree	5	6.8	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.11 provides the perceptions of respondents The knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; more than 75.7% of respondents confirmed that the knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 14.9 % of respondent disagreed that the knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The 9.5% respondents have been undecided that the knowledge and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 75.7% respondents confirmed that knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.14: The growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The growing and processing of tea		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	36	48.6	48.6
	Agree	22	29.7	78.4
	Undecided	6	8.1	86.5
	Disagree	8	10.8	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.12 illustrates data about the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; out of 100% respondents, 78.4% of respondents confirmed that the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 13.5% of respondent disagreed that the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and 8.1% respondents have been undecided the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 89.2% respondents confirmed the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.15: The distribution process is influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The distribution process		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	28	37.8	37.8
	Agree	33	44.6	82.4
	Undecided	5	6.8	89.2
	Disagree	5	6.8	95.9
	Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.13 provides the perceptions of respondents about distribution process are influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. These are confirmed by 82.4% of respondents in relation to the distribution process is influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 10.9% of respondent refused that distribution process is influential

factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and 6.8% respondents have been undecided that distribution process is influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 82.4% of respondents confirmed that distribution process is influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.16: Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Market availability of tea of COPTHE	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	35	47.3	47.3
Agree	26	35.1	82.4
Valid Undecided	5	6.8	89.2
Disagree	5	6.8	95.9
Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.14 provides the information on the perceptions of respondents about Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA where 82.4% of respondents confirmed that Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 10.9% of respondent did not agree with the idea said that Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and 6.8% respondents have been undecided that Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 82.4% respondents confirmed that Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.1.3 The effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Tea farmers' welfare is based on the proportion of population living below the poverty line is associated with the time factor and the fact that restricted itself to welfare based on tea income. The farmers' welfare is looked that leading export crop with a history of the well-organized institutions that are envied by other crops' enterprises and improving returns (Gesimba, et al., 2005). During the study at COOPTHE SHAGASHA, the researcher confirmed that there are various effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE

SHAGASHA which are the increase of Income for farmers; enhancing in savings per month; beneficiaries are able housing; access to food or nutrition; increase of household assets; access to education; access to the health care; beneficiaries have confidence; and creating new businesses of members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA as various tables below presented.

Table 4.17: Increase of Income for farmers

Increase of Income	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	29	39.2	39.2
Agree	39	52.7	91.9
Valid Undecided	3	4.1	95.9
Disagree	2	2.7	98.6
Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.15 shows the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA on how they are increased in the income after joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This confirmed by 91.9% respondents who said that there is an increase of Income for farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. 4.1% respondents have been undecided about an increase of income for farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. 4.1% of respondents were strongly disagreed and disagreed about an increase of income for farmers. According to majority of 91.9% respondents who confirmed this idea, the researcher also said that there is an Increase of Income for farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA since 2013-2017.

Table 4.18: Enhancing in Savings per month

Enhancing in Savings	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	43	58.1	58.1
Agree	22	29.7	87.8
Valid Undecided	6	8.1	95.9
Disagree	2	2.7	98.6
Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.16 presents the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA on enhancing in Savings per month from harvest obtained in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. More than 87.8% of respondents confirmed that farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA enhance savings per month. The 8.1% respondents have undecided on enhancing savings per month. The 4 .1% of respondents were strongly disagreed and disagreed about enhancing savings per month. Generally majority of 91.9% respondents confirmed the farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA enhance savings per month from harvest obtained during 2015 to 2017.

Table 4.19: Beneficiaries are able housing

Being able housing	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	30	40.5	40.5
Agree	36	48.6	89.2
Undecided	2	2.7	91.9
Disagree	4	5.4	97.3
Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.17 illustrates the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in relation with beneficiaries were able housing their own houses. This confirmed by 89.2% respondents who said they were able housing after joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The 2.7% respondents were undecided, this means they did not show any ideas about beneficiaries who were able housing. The 8.1% of respondents were strongly disagreed and disagreed about beneficiaries of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able housing. According to data collected at COOPTHE SHAGASHA, 89.2% respondents confirmed they were able housing their own houses after joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.20: Farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family

Access to food or nutrition	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	35	47.3	47.3
Agree	31	41.9	89.2
Undecided	5	6.8	95.9
Disagree	1	1.4	97.3
Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.18 presents the agreements of respondents from COOPTHE SHAGASHA on how farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family. Out of 100.0% respondents, more than 89.2% respondents confirmed that Farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family. The 6.8% respondents have undecided on farmers of COPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family. Only 4.1% of respondents refused those farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family. Majority of 89.2% respondents confirmed that farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family.

Table 4.21: Increase of household assets

Household assets for members of COPTHE	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	33	44.6	44.6
Agree	33	44.6	89.2
Undecided	3	4.1	93.2
Disagree	2	2.7	95.9
Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.19 presents the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA on how they are increased in household assets. This confirmed by 89.2% respondents who said that there is an increase of household assets for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The

4.1% respondents' undecided about Increase of household assets. The 6.8% of respondents disagreed about an Increase of household assets. Majority of 89.2% respondents from COOPTHE SHAGASHA confirmed that there is an increase of household assets.

Table 4.22: Beneficiaries access to education

Access to education	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	32	43.2	43.2
Agree	35	47.3	90.5
Valid Undecided	2	2.7	93.2
Disagree	4	5.4	98.6
Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.20 shows the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA on how Beneficiaries access to education. Out of 100.0% respondents, 90.5% respondents confirmed that beneficiary's access to education. The 2.7% of respondents have been undecided about Beneficiaries access to education. The 6.8% of respondents disagreed about beneficiaries' access to education. Majority of 90.5% respondents from COOPTHE SHAGASHA confirmed that Beneficiaries access to education.

Table 4.23: Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA Access to the health care

Access to the health care	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	30	40.5	40.5
Agree	36	48.6	89.2
Valid Undecided	4	5.4	94.6
Disagree	2	2.7	97.3
Strongly Disagree	2	2.7	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.21 shows the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA about members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to the health care. This confirmed by 89.2% respondents who said that Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA Access to the health

care. The 5.4% respondents have been undecided about Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA Access to the health care. The 5.4% of respondents were strongly disagreed and disagreed on how Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to the health care. According to the majority of 89.2% respondents Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA Access to the health care.

Table 4.24: Beneficiaries have confidence

Creating confidence		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	38	51.4	51.4
	Agree	26	35.1	86.5
	Undecided	3	4.1	90.5
	Disagree	4	5.4	95.9
	Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.22 illustrates the perceptions of respondents on the beneficiaries have confidence. Among of 100.0% respondents, more than 86.5% respondents confirmed that Beneficiaries have confidence. The 4.1% respondents undecided about beneficiaries have confidence. The 9.5% of respondents disagreed about Beneficiaries have confidence. Majority of 86.5% respondents confirmed that Beneficiaries have confidence.

Table 4.25: Members of COPTHE create new businesses

New businesses		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	37	50.0	50.0
	Agree	23	31.1	81.1
	Undecided	7	9.5	90.5
	Disagree	4	5.4	95.9
	Strongly Disagree	3	4.1	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.23 illustrates the perceptions of respondents' members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA on how Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA create new businesses. This confirmed by 81.1% respondents who said that there is Members of COOPTHE

SHAGASHA create new businesses. The 9.5 % respondents have been undecided about Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA create new businesses. The 9.5% of respondents were strongly disagreed and disagreed about Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA create new businesses. According to majority of 81.1% respondents who confirmed this idea, the researcher also said that there is Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA create new businesses.

4.1.4 The correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Literally, a tea farming household was considered to be poor if returns from tea enterprise were less than its financial requirement to meet basic needs. Household financial requirements were based on the number of adult equivalent and the cost of buying basket of necessities. The welfare level was net of return from tea enterprise (tea income less operation costs of tea framing) minus the household costs of basic necessities. A positive results indicated household able to meet basic requirements and hence above the poverty line. The tables below show that the perceptions of respondents on the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

Table 4.26: Farming tea increase income and savings per month for tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in previous years

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	37	50.0	50.0
Valid Agree	37	50.0	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.24 illustrates the perceptions of respondents on Farming tea increase income and savings per month for tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in Shagasha in previous years. All of 100.0% respondents participated in this study at COOPTHE SHAGASHA confirmed Farming tea increase income and savings per month for tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in previous years

Table 4.27: Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	36	48.6	48.6
Agree	33	44.6	93.2
Undecided	2	2.7	95.9
Disagree	2	2.7	98.6
Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.25 illustrates the perception of respondents on Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Out of 100.0% respondents of COOPTHE SHAGASHA, more than 93.2% of respondents confirmed that Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Only 2.7% respondents were Undecided about Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The 4.1% respondents disagreed that Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Generally more than 93.2% respondents confirmed that Tea farming has change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA

Table 4.28: With tea farming, tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	33	44.6	44.6
Agree	34	45.9	90.5
Undecided	5	6.8	97.3
Disagree	1	1.4	98.6
Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	100.0
Total	74	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Table 4.26 illustrates the perception of respondents in relation with tea farming; tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs. More than

90.5% respondents confirmed that with tea farming, tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs. The 6.8% respondents were undecided on with tea farming; tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs. Only 2.8% respondents disagreed that with tea farming, tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs.

Table 4.29: How could you compare the level of Income for farmers before and after adopting tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA?

Income per month “RWF”	Income before joining tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA		Income after joining with tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
20,000 – 40,000	35	47.3	7	9.5
40,000 – 60,000	30	40.5	8	10.8
60,000 – 80,000	6	8.1	5	6.7
80,000 – 100,000	2	2.7	35	47.3
100,000 and above	1	1.4	19	25.7
Total	74	100.0	74	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2018

The table 4.27 illustrate data in relation with comparison of level of Income of beneficiaries before and after joining tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. On the side of Income of beneficiaries before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; out of 100.0% respondents, 47.3% respondents confirmed that they received income between 20,000 – 40,000Frw per month; 40.5% received from 40,000 – 60,000frw of income per month; 8.1% respondents said that they obtained income per month between 60,000 – 80,000frw; 2.7% respondents confirmed that they received income between 80,000 – 100,000 frw; and 1.4% received income per month of 100,000frw and above.

On side of Income of beneficiaries after joined tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, data from 100.0% respondents confirmed that less than 9.5% still receiving income from 20,000 – 40,000frw; 10.8% respondents obtained income per month from 40,000 up to 60,000frw; the 6.7% respondents said that they are increased on income per month from 60,000 up to

80,000frw; 47.3% respondents confirmed increased their income per month from 80,000 to 100,000frw; the 25.7% respondents confirmed after joining tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA services they received income per month of 100,000frw and above.

During this study in comparison of income of beneficiaries before and after joining tea farming in COPTHE, the researcher found that beneficiaries before joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA, majorities obtained lower income per month, while after joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, Income per month received was increased comparing to what they received before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This means to join tea farming Cooperative has a greater role because it increases the income per month to the farmers of tea.

Table 4.30: How could you compare the level of savings before and after adopting tea farming?

Savings per month “RWF”	Money saved per month before tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA		Money saved per month after tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
5,000 – 10,000	20	27.0	2	2.7
11,000 – 20,000	24	32.4	3	4.1
21,000 – 30,000	15	20.3	1	1.4
31,000 – 40,000	2	2.7	5	6.8
41,000 – 50,000	3	4.1	6	8.1
51,000 – 60,000	1	1.4	4	5.4
61,000 – 70,000	2	2.7	10	13.5
71,000 – 80,000	1	1.4	11	14.9
81,000 – 90,000	2	2.7	14	18.9
91,000 – 100,000	2	2.7	10	13.5
101,000 and above	2	2.7	8	10.8
Total	74	100.0	74	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Literally, savings, according to Keynesian economics, consists of the amount left over when the cost of a person's consumer expenditure is subtracted from the amount of disposable income he earns in a given period of time. For those who are financially prudent, the amount of money left over after personal expenses have been met can be positive; for those who tend to rely on credit and loans to make ends meet, there is no money left for savings.

During this study, the researcher found that savings for beneficiaries before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA were lower than savings after joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This is an indicator of contribution of tea farming in Cooperative welfare of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in Shagasha as the table 4.28 presented for example, the beneficiaries who saved 101,000 RWF and above per month before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA were 2.7% while after joining tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA, saving were increased until to 10.8% of farmers of tea in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.1.5 Correlation Coefficient Analysis Test

This section also concentrates on analysis of how effectiveness of Tea Farming contributes to the Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. All responses related to the questions on effectiveness of Tea Farming were summarized to generate a representative independent variable while all responses related to the Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA were totaled to give the dependent variable. In correlating using Spearman analysis the research got table 4.29 as follows:

Table 4.31: Correlations

			Effectiveness of Tea Farming	Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA
Spearman' s rho	Effectiveness of Tea Farming	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.735**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	74	74
	Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA	Correlation Coefficient	.735**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	74	74

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the table 4.29, P-value equals to 0.000 which less than Alpha (0.05). This is an indicator of relationship between effectiveness of Tea Farming and Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The level of relationship is $R_s = .735$ (i.e 73.5%) located in interval $0.7 \leq \rho < 0.9$ categorized as high Correlation. Significant level is 0.01 (1%), the P-Value of 0.000 (0%) which is less than 1% (Alpha). In other words, when effectiveness of Tea Farming is effectively performed, Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA is more increased. This is correlated at a high level and this normal for social sciences whereby strong or perfect correlation is found in exact sciences. This helps to confirm that there is significant relationship between effectiveness of Tea Farming and Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.2 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The major concern of this analysis was to assess the effectiveness of Tea Farming for the Tea Farmer's Welfare in Rwanda especially members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. Questionnaires were distributed to the 74 respondents selected from members of this agriculture cooperative, and they were given one week and two days of responding to the questions. The participation rate was 100.0% of responding. The findings indicated that the 63.5% respondents were males, while 36.5% of respondents were females in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.2.1 Findings on the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The results were shown on table 4.6 to table 4.14 indicated that more than 82.4% of respondents confirmed that Tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan; 81.1% of respondents confirmed that care and experience of the farmers' influences tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 78.4% of respondents confirmed that the composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 83.8% respondents confirmed Farm Management affect tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA 89.2% respondents confirmed climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 75.7% respondents confirmed that knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA 89.2% respondents confirmed the growing and processing of tea affect tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 82.4% of

respondents confirmed that distribution process is influential factor of tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and 82.4% respondents confirmed that Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

4.2.2 Findings on the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The findings indicated that 91.9% respondents who said that there is an increase of Income for farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 87.8% of respondents confirmed that farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA enhance savings per month; 89.2% respondents who said they were able housing after joining COOPTHE SHAGASHA; more than 89.2% respondents confirmed that Farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA access to food or nutrition for their family; this confirmed by 89.2% respondents who said that there is an increase of household assets for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA; 90.5% respondents confirmed that beneficiary's access to education; 89.2% respondents who said that Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA Access to the health care. Majority of 86.5% respondents confirmed that Beneficiaries have confidence and 81.1% respondents who confirmed this idea, the researcher also said that there is Members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA create new businesses.

4.2.3 Findings on the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA

The findings confirmed that all of 100.0% respondents participated in this study at COOPTHE SHAGASHA confirmed Farming tea increase income and savings per month for tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in previous years. 93.2% respondents confirmed that Tea farming has change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. 90.5% respondents confirmed that with tea farming, tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs. The table 4.27 illustrate data in relation with comparison of level of Income of beneficiaries before and after joining tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. On the side of Income of beneficiaries before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; out of 100.0% respondents, 47.3% respondents confirmed that they received income between 20,000 – 40,000Frw per month; 40.5% received from 40,000 – 60,000frw of income per month; 8.1% respondents said that they obtained income per month between 60,000 – 80,000frw; 2.7% respondents confirmed that they received income between 80,000 – 100,000 frw; and 1.4% received income per month of 100,000frw and above.

On side of Income of beneficiaries after joined tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA, data from 100.0% respondents confirmed that less than 9.5% still receiving income from 20,000 – 40,000frw; 10.8% respondents obtained income per month from 40,000 up to 60,000frw; the 6.7% respondents said that they are increased on income per month from 60,000 up to 80,000frw; 47.3% respondents confirmed increased their income per month from 80,000 to 100,000frw; the 25.7% respondents confirmed after joining tea farming of COOPTHE SHAGASHA services they received income per month of 100,000frw and above. During this study, the researcher found that savings for beneficiaries before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA were lower than savings after joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This is an indicator of contribution of tea farming in Cooperative welfare of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in Shagasha as the table 4.28 presented for example, the beneficiaries who saved 101,000 RWF and above per month before joining tea farming in COOPTHE SHAGASHA were 2.7% while after joining tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA, saving were increased until to 10.8% of farmers of tea in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

From the table 4.29, P-value equals to 0.000 which less than Alpha (0.05). This is an indicator of relationship between effectiveness of Tea Farming and Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. The level of relationship is $R_s = .735$ (i.e 73.5%) located in interval $0.7 \leq \rho < 0.9$ categorized as high Correlation. In other words, when effectiveness of Tea Farming is effectively performed, Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA is more increased. This is correlated at a high level and this normal for social sciences whereby strong or perfect correlation is found in exact sciences. This helps to confirm that there is significant relationship between effectiveness of Tea Farming and Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the conclusions on basis to the findings indicated in this research paper and showing the recommendations to different parts. The major concern of this study was to assess the effectiveness of Tea Farming for the Tea Farmer's Welfare in Rwanda, with a case study of COOPTHE SHAGASHA (2015-2017).

The specific objectives were to find out the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA; to assess the effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA; and to determine the correlation between tea farming and welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This study attempted to find out how does effectiveness of tea farming influence the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda especially COOPTHE SHAGASHA's members.

The research design applied were qualitative and quantitative approaches and descriptive and correlation research designs. The target population was 325 members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA. This sample size was 74 respondents. The findings indicated that the 63.5% respondents were males, while 36.5% of respondents were females in COOPTHE SHAGASHA.

5.1 CONCLUSION

Gedela (2012) studies the factors influencing the household welfare in Africa. He observes that most households in developing countries are poor, risk averse and operate in scenarios of uncertainty and imperfect financial markets hence the above theories are deficient in explaining the saving behavior of such households. The effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers provide a background to understanding the health scenario in a country. These indicators for the country as well as states help in identifying the linkages between socio-economic indicators and achievement of health goals.

The findings indicated that there are various influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA as the results were shown on table 4.6 to table 4.14. The findings indicated that there are effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA as majority of respondents confirmed it. It was found that tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA influences welfare of tea farmers. As conclusion according to the findings

obtained in the above, the objectives of this study were achieved, problem was solved and research questions were answered.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Data from COOPTHE SHAGASHA confirmed that Tea Farming contributes 73.5% to Tea Farmer's Welfare. COOPTHE SHAGASHA is advised to enhance the trainings for members in relation with the tea farming in order to enhance Tea Farmer's Welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA on 100.0%.

5.3 SUGGESTIONS TO FURTHER STUDY

The future researchers are advised to take this document as reference by considering other elements to show also the result of tea farmer's welfare in COOPTHE SHAGASHA and accomplish what the researcher did not reach. The suggested topics to be accomplished were:

- i. The effect of Care and experience in tea farming on tea farmers in agriculture cooperative in Rwanda
- ii. The role of Farm Management in tea farming on the tea farming in cooperative in Rwanda

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE ADDRESSED TO MEMBERS OF COOP THE SHAGASHA

Dear respondent,

I'm Lameck NIYONZIMA, a finalist year student at KIBOGORA POLYTECHNIC in faculty of BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES, department of Economics and Management. I am conducting a study on the “**effectiveness of tea farming for the tea farmer's welfare in Rwanda, a case study of COOP THE SHAGASHA (2015 - 2017)**”.

All students in final year are required to do a research project in order to complete Bachelor's Degree. You have been therefore selected to participate in this important exercise and your contribution and support will be highly appreciated. The information that you will give shall be treated as confidential as possible and used solely for academic purposes.

Thank you for your support

Lameck NIYONZIMA

Instructions

- ✓ To answer, it is enough to tick in the corresponding box or corresponding rating scales;
- ✓ Where you are going to formulate the answer in your own words, please use the reserved space.
- ✓ Using the levels of agreement or disagreement shown below:

SD: Strongly Disagree; **D:** Disagree; **A:** Agree; **SA:** Strongly Agree; **U:** Undecided

Likert five Point Scales

Weight Scale	Interpretation	Descriptions
5	Strongly agree	Agreeing without doubt
4	Agree	agreeing with some doubt
3	Undecided	Neutrality of respondents
2	Disagree	Disagreeing with some doubt
1	Strongly disagree	Disagreeing without doubt

PART I: PERSONAL PROFILE OF RESPONDENT

1) Age of respondents

19-35

36-45

45-65

Above 65

2) Gender

Male

Female

3) Level of education

Masters and above

Bachelors' degree

Secondary level

Other qualification specify.....

4) Marital status

Single

Married

Widowed

divorced

5) Experiences in COOP THE SHAGASHA

Less than 1 year

1 to 2 years

2 to 3 years

3 to 4 years

4 to 5 years

5 years and above

PART II: DATA PROFILE: QUESTIONS ON TEA FARMING

Please tick (V) in front of statements shown in the tables below to indicate the levels of agreement or disagreement by using the keys: **SD:** Strongly Disagree; **D:** Disagree; **A:** Agree; **SA:** Strongly Agree; **U:** Undecided

6. What are the influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA?

The influential factors of tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA' members	SD	D	A	SA	U
i. Tea farming influenced by type of tea plant, and the health of the plan					
ii. Care and experience of the farmers influences tea farming at COOPTHE SHAGASHA					
iii. The composition of the soil is a primary contributor to the health of the plant in tea farming					
iv. Farm Management affect tea farming for COOPTHE SHAGASHA' members					
v. The climate in which the tea plants growing is factor of tea farming					
vi. The knowledge, and skill employed in the processing of the tea leaves lead to tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA					
vii. The growing and processing of tea affect tea farming COOPTHE SHAGASHA					
viii. The distribution process is influential factor of tea farming					
ix. Market availability of tea influences tea farming for members of COOPTHE SHAGASHA					

PART III: QUESTIONS ON WELFARE STYLE OF COOPTHE SHAGASHA MEMBERS

7. What are effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers in COOPTHE SHAGASHA?

The effective indicators of welfare of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA	SD	D	A	SA	U
i. Increase of Income for farmers					
ii. Enhancing in Savings per month					
iii. Beneficiaries are able housing					

iv. They access to food or nutrition;					
v. Increase of household assets					
vi. Beneficiaries access to education;					
vii. Access to the health care;					
viii. Beneficiaries have confidence					
ix. Creating new businesses					

8. What is the contribution of tea farming on tea farmers of COPTHE SHAGASHA?

contribution of tea farming on tea farmers of COPTHE SHAGASHA	SD	D	A	SA	U
i. Farming tea increase income and savings per month for tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA in previous years					
ii. Tea farming have change positively the life style of tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA					
iii. With tea farming, tea farmers of COOPTHE SHAGASHA were able to satisfy their household premium needs					

PART IV: INDICATORS OF TEA FARMER'S WELFARE

How could you compare the level of Income for farmers before and after adopting tea farming?

Income per month "RWF"	Income before joining tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA	Income after joining with tea farming COOPTHE SHAGASHA
20,000 – 40,000		
40,000 – 60,000		
60,000 – 80,000		
80,000 – 100,000		
100,000 and above		

How could you compare the level of savings before and after adopting tea farming?

Savings per month “RWF”	Money saved per month before tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA	Money saved per month after tea farming with COOPTHE SHAGASHA
5,000 – 10,000		
11,000 – 20,000		
21,000 – 30,000		
31,000 – 40,000		
41,000 – 50,000		
51,000 – 60,000		
61,000 – 70,000		
71,000 – 80,000		
81,000 – 90,000		
91,000 – 100,000		
101,000 and above		

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATION